

National Aeronautics and Space Administration

Outreach and Educational Activity Training Webinar for NASA Total Solar Eclipse SunSpots and Other Engagement Sites

Wednesdays, 4 - 5 pm ET, Feb 14 - March 20

Hosted by NASA HEAT

NASA Heliophysics Education Activation Team
Principal Investigator: Dr. Michael Kirk

Logistics

- This webinar will be recorded.
- Please keep microphones on mute.
- Feel free to use the chat to ask questions and share resources.

About NASA HEAT

NASA Heliophysics Education Activation Team

PI: Dr. Michael Kirk

- Provides educational guidance and resources for educators, communicators, and learners of all ages to deepen their understanding of our Sun, its effects on Earth and the solar system.
- Increases heliophysics literacy and deepen public understanding about NASA Science by uniting existing NASA Science Mission Directorate (SMD) assets with educators, learners of all ages, and communities across the country.
- Collects legacy resources, creates new heliophysics resources, connects resources to classroom concepts and current NASA missions through a Framework for Heliophysics Education, and disseminates resources in a dynamic searchable Heliophysics Resource Database. <https://science.nasa.gov/learn/heat/>

What is a NASA Solar Eclipse SunSpot?

What is a sunspot?

Sunspots are cooler spots on the Sun where there is a high concentration of magnetic fields.

One of the largest sunspots in the last nine years, labeled AR1944, was seen in early January 2014. An image of Earth has been added for scale.

Credits: NASA/SDO

What is a NASA Solar Eclipse SunSpot?

A location (on Earth) along the path of totality where NASA will support solar eclipse viewing events. Like Sunspots on the Sun, these locations will be the coolest places to view the total solar eclipse!

NASA will send exhibits, speakers, and eclipse glasses to dozens of designated SunSpots across the path of totality. These locations will include areas and events that are free to the public.

NASA Solar Eclipse SunSpots

NASA Hosted SunSpot Locations

Credit: NASA/Scientific Visualization Studio/Michala Garrison; Ernie Wright/NASA Goddard Space Flight Center, and NASA HEAT

Along with the NASA Hosted events, there will be hundreds of other locations along the path with a NASA presence.

NASA Hosted	Events with NASA-led engagement. Some SunSpots will broadcast live from the site.
NASA Affiliated	Events hosted by NASA partners, for example the NASA Space Grant Consortium and partnering universities
NASA Speaker	Events with a NASA speaker

If you can't make it to a NASA SunSpot, you can still participate in the magic of totality anywhere along the path. If you can't get to the path of totality, you can still enjoy a partial solar eclipse!

Find out more about SunSpot locations and events at solarsystem.nasa.gov/eclipses

NASA Science for the 2024 Solar Eclipse

Credit: NASA/NOAA

During the total solar eclipse various science experiments will be done to increase our understanding of the Sun-Earth-Moon relationship.

It is a chance to observe the effects of what happens when the Sun is temporarily blocked, when viewed from a small area of Earth.

During a total solar eclipse, NASA is interested in:

- Learning more about outstanding solar science concepts like the connections between the low and mid corona.
- Learning more about outstanding atmospheric science through the observation of eclipse-induced changes in the atmosphere under the shadow of the Moon.
- Using satellites, suborbital rockets, high-altitude balloons, and other NASA assets to observe the eclipse and its effects.
- Testing the design and function of new hardware in the unique eclipse conditions.

NASA Funded Citizen Science for 2024

NASA welcomes members of the public to participate voluntarily in the process of science.

This composite image shows the progression of a total solar eclipse, from right to left, in Madras, Oregon, on Aug. 21, 2017.

Credits: NASA/Aubrey Gemignani

In addition to the more than thirty existing NASA funded citizen science projects, NASA has awarded funding for science teams to conduct citizen science investigations as a total solar eclipse sweeps across North America on April 8, 2024.

In these experiments, volunteers will help study the Sun and its corona, which is revealed when the Moon completely covers the Sun's bright disk.

Follow the development of these projects and learn how to get involved at solarsystem.nasa.gov/eclipses

- **SunSketcher 2024: An Eclipse Movie Across America** [Western Kentucky University]
- **Geo Collaborate: Sharing Eclipse Data for Broadcasters and Educators** [StormCenter Communications, Inc.]
- **The DEB Initiative: Documenting the Corona Moment by Moment** [Southern Illinois University]
- **CATE 2024: Capturing Polarized Views of the Corona** [Southwest Research Institute]
- **Eclipse Megamovie 2024: Recording Dynamics Across the Corona** [Sonoma State University]
- **'Listening Party' for Amateur Radio Operators** [University of Scranton]

In this training, you will get...

- Links to **full activity instructions** - for longer engagement opportunities in classrooms and out-of-school-time spaces
- Access to abbreviated **“Tabletop Instructions”** & **talking points** - for outreach events
- **How-to video** of the activity
- **Q & A** with NASA HEAT educators

Credit: NASA Goddard

“Tabletop Instructions” are one-page informational displays for quick reference at busy outreach events.

Talking points are printed on the back of the Tabletop Instructions to help communicate the key science.

NASA HEAT Planned SunSpot Activities

Activities Planned for the NASA Exhibit on April 8, 2024 @ the Dallas Arboretum

- ✓ Eclipse Essentials: Safe and Stylish Solar Viewing Glasses
- ✓ 2024 Total Solar Eclipse US Map Pinhole Projector Activity
- ✓ Predict the Corona Activities
- ✓ UltraViolet (UV) Light-Reactive Bead Investigation
- ✓ Plus! How to Photograph a Solar Eclipse

And get links to other solar eclipse activities from our NASA partners!

Eclipse Essentials: Safe and Stylish Solar Viewing Glasses

➤ Full Activity Instructions

- ★ Activity Overview
- ★ Materials List
- ★ Detailed Steps
- ★ Tips and Tricks
- ★ Safety Reminders

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Eclipse Essentials: Safe and Stylish Solar Eclipse Glasses

Next Generation Science Standard MS.ESS1-1 - Develop and use a model of the Earth-Sun-Moon system to describe the cyclic patterns of lunar phases, eclipses of the Sun and Moon, and seasons.

Overview:
Keep solar viewing safe, easy, and fun with this hands-on, art-infused, 25- to 30-minute activity for audiences of all ages. Engage learners in the wonders of solar viewing by having them personalize their solar eclipse glasses.

Materials:

- ☐ Solar Eclipse Glasses (ISO 12312-2 Safety Standard)
- ☐ Paper Plate or Cardstock
- ☐ Pen or Pencil
- ☐ Scissors
- ☐ Tape
- ☐ Optional Supplies: Hole puncher, stapler, ruler, markers, crayons, glitter glue, feathers, adhesive gemstones, stickers, ribbon, etc.

Steps:

1. Use the eclipse glasses as a template to mark the score lines on the paper plate or cardstock, following the guidelines shown in the diagram below.
2. Cut along the score lines and make the two slits for the ear pieces to slide into.
3. Slide the earpieces into each slit and adhere the glasses to the plate/cardstock by taping along the inside of the ear piece slits.
4. Optional: Modify your design to make a crown, flowers, or any shape of your choice.
5. Observe! Use the glasses to safely observe the Sun during a solar eclipse, or at any time!

Note: Decorating the paper plate or cardstock is optional. Have learners decorate the plates prior to inserting the glasses, or protect the lenses of the eclipse glasses by covering them with paper while decorating. Do not view the Sun with damaged or scratched lenses.

Credit: NASA HEAT/Shannon Reed

Width of eclipse glasses
Slits for ear pieces
Vertical lines to create an opening for the lower face

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Eclipse Essentials: Safe and Stylish Solar Eclipse Glasses

Tips and Tricks:

Safety Comes First:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ensure that the eclipse glasses are certified (ISO 12312-2 safety standard).• Follow guidelines and safety instructions for safe eclipse viewing.
Selecting Accessories:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Consider using a variety of lightweight materials like colored tapes, stickers, or adhesive decorations.• Make sure the accessories do not impede visibility through the lenses or interfere with the effectiveness of the glasses.
Creative Stylization:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Let learners' imagination run wild and personalize their eclipse glasses with their own unique style. Have them experiment with different colors, patterns, or designs that resonate with their personal preferences and creativity.• Explore themes related to celestial events or nature for an added touch of uniqueness.
Secure Attachment Techniques:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Discover techniques to securely attach accessories to the personalized glasses without compromising safety. Consider punching holes in the ear pieces and attaching the glasses with ribbon (see images below).• Ensure that any attachments do not impede visibility through the lenses or interfere with the effectiveness of the glasses.
Maintenance and Care:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Regularly inspect eclipse glasses to ensure that the accessories are securely attached and do not pose any risks.• Store the glasses in a safe place when not in use to prevent scratches or damage.
Observe and Enjoy:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Look up! Enjoy the dynamic view, have fun, and be safe in your super cool eclipse glasses!

Credit: JAXA/NASA/SOHO/NAGI Credit: NASA/Alamy Gengshou

Use your decorated glasses to view two upcoming solar eclipses in North America.

Different types of eclipses have different safety guidelines. If you choose to use solar eclipse glasses for solar viewing during a partial solar eclipse or annular solar eclipse, solar eclipse glasses must be worn at all times. During a total solar eclipse, only those observers in the path of totality may remove their eclipse glasses during the brief period of totality, when the Moon completely blocks the Sun. Learn more about these upcoming solar eclipses and solar viewing safety at [solarsystem.nasa.gov/eclipses](https://science.nasa.gov/eclipses).

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<https://science.nasa.gov/resource/eclipses-essentials-safe-and-stylish-solar-viewing-glasses/>

Eclipse Essentials: Safe and Stylish Solar Viewing Glasses

➤ Abbreviated Tabletop Instructions & Talking Points for Outreach Events

Pro Tip!

Precut the plates before your event to save time and reduce the risk of injury associated with visitors handling sharp objects.

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Eclipse Essentials: Safe and Stylish Solar Viewing Glasses

Steps:

1. Decorate the pre-cut template.
2. Slide the earpieces into each slit, taking care not to damage the lenses.
3. Prevent light from seeping in by taping the top of the glasses to the plate and on the inside of the plate.
4. Observe the Sun safely and stylishly anytime!

Slide the earpieces into the slits.

Tape the top of the glasses to the inside of the mask.

Explore the Full Activity:
science.nasa.gov/learn/heat/resource/eclipse-essentials-safe-and-stylish-solar-viewing-glasses/

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NP-2022-3-080-GSFC

science.nasa.gov/learn/heat

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Eclipse Essentials: Safe and Stylish Solar Viewing Glasses

Talking Points

- Are you ready for the total solar eclipse tomorrow (today)?
 - Do you have the tools you need to be safe?
 - Solar Viewing glasses are one tool you can use to safely view the Sun.
 - You can use these glasses to view the Sun anytime, but they are especially useful during a partial solar eclipse.
- **Tomorrow's eclipse will start as a partial eclipse and then become a total solar eclipse. (Approximate times for Dallas, TX)**
 - The partial eclipse begins at approximately 12:23 pm as the Moon's shadow starts to obscure part of the Sun.
 - Slowly, the Sun will become more and more obscured, until the Sun is 100% blocked at approximately 1:40 pm.
 - At that point, you can take off your solar viewing glasses for about 4 minutes during totality. This is the only time it is safe to look directly at the Sun without special equipment. The Moon's shadow is blocking the light that would otherwise damage your eyes.
 - You will have to put your glasses back on at approximately 1:44 pm, when the Moon's shadow starts to move away from the Sun.
 - You can continue to watch the partial solar eclipse until approximately 3:02 pm, when the shadow moves completely off of the Sun.
 - These times can vary, slightly, even within the city limits. Use the map on <https://www.nasa.gov/public/eclipse-map-2024/> to find accurate times for your exact location in your city.
- During totality you will be able to see the Sun's outer atmosphere, the corona. We usually can't see the corona because it is much dimmer than the bright surface of the Sun.
 - Scientists take this opportunity to make observations of the corona and learn more about how the Sun affects Earth.
- Save your solar eclipse glasses and use them anytime to make observations of the Sun!
 - Store them in a safe place and make sure there are no holes or scratches on the lenses.

science.nasa.gov/learn/heat

Enter the correct times for your location.

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1151f1Z-YXOoA6r06djd-vfC9duZ9rTk/view?usp=share_link

Check the Times for your Location

National Solar Observatory

<https://nso.edu/for-public/eclipse-map-2024/>

Exploratorium

<https://www.exploratorium.edu/eclipse/2024-total-solar-eclipse-guide>

Eclipse Soundscapes

<https://eclipsesoundscapes.org/eclipse-lookup-tool/>

Eclipse Essentials: Safe and Stylish Solar Viewing Glasses

➤ How-to Video

Materials

- ❑ Solar Viewing Glasses
- ❑ White paper plates, with the mouth/nose space and earpiece slits precut
 - ❑ Scissors
 - ❑ Exacto knife
- ❑ Materials for decoration
 - ❑ Markers
 - ❑ Stickers
 - ❑ Adhesive gemstones
 - ❑ Optional: “kid” scissors for creating shapes along the edges of the plate
- ❑ Clear gift tape

Where can I get solar viewing glasses?

- Solar viewing glasses are not the same as sunglasses. They block all visible light and harmful UV light.
- Contact your local library or university to inquire if they are distributing to the community.
- If you choose to purchase the glasses via a retailer, make sure the solar viewing glasses have an international safety rating of **ISO 12312-2**.

Video: How to check your solar viewing glasses

<https://youtu.be/XKnj9C36rTE?si=-QSW0HudC7jkHGxL>

Learn More:
<https://eclipse.aas.org/eye-safety/iso-certification>

Discussion Questions

- What questions do you have about this activity?
- How would you modify this activity for your audiences?
- What other activities have you done that are similar to this one?

You are invited to add your ideas to the chat or raise your hand to share with the group.

How many people plan on doing this activity at their event?

2024 Total Solar Eclipse U.S. Pinhole Projector Map

➤ **3D Print Files (and all files) are also available on NASA's 3D Resource site**

2024 Total Solar Eclipse - USA Map - NASA Pinhole Projector

Description

Author/Origin: NASA HEAT/J. Patrick Haas

Relevant Mission: Total Solar Eclipse 2024

Date Added: February 13, 2023

Keywords: Eclipse

Download the Zip file which includes the 2D Paper Cut and the 3D Print versions of the US annular eclipse map, along with activity directions for engaging learners. For specific file usage be sure to review the READ.me.

<https://nasa3d.arc.nasa.gov/detail/usa-eclipse-2024>

Percentage of obscuration at locations across the country.

2024 Total Solar Eclipse U.S. Pinhole Projector Map

➤ Abbreviated Tabletop Instructions & Talking Points for Outreach Events

3-5 minute engagement

Pro Tip!

Precut or die-cut the paper maps before your event to save time.

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Ddba6G1mnlFakSzr9lwOB0oFoSJ7N1Nf/view?usp=share_link

2024 Total Solar Eclipse US Map Projector Activity

Your back should always be to the Sun when using a pinhole projector. Do NOT look at the Sun through the projector.

Steps:

1. Choose the **square, triangle or heart** hole punch on the map where you live.
2. **Make a prediction!** What shape will the Sun be when the sunlight shines through the holes in the map of the image on a piece of paper for a better image?
3. **Standing with your back toward the Sun**, hold approximately three feet above the ground, out in sunlight to shine through the holes in the map of the image on a piece of paper for a better image.
4. **Experiment!** What happens when you move the map away from the ground?

Circle Hole Punch Star Hole Punch

Place a piece of paper to see the shadow.

2024 Total Solar Eclipse Projector Activity Talking Points

- **Another tool you can use to observe a solar eclipse.**
 - Even if you have solar viewing glasses, different and interesting way to observe try both tools during the duration of the eclipse.
 - A pinhole projector is an indirect method of observing the eclipse.
- **The map shows the percentage of the Moon's shadow at different locations.**
 - Observers on the "100% line" of the solar eclipse.
 - All other locations will experience a partial eclipse.
- **No matter what shape you project the shape of the Sun, not the shape of the Moon's shadow at different locations.**
 - The Sun is normally round. Try the projector at different locations.
 - During the solar eclipse, you can observe changes as the Moon's shadow covers the solar eclipse progresses.

How does a Pinhole Projector Work?

Talking Points

- **Pinhole projectors** allowed early scientists to view the shapes of illuminated objects, like the Sun, by shining the light from the object through a very small hole, projecting the image onto the ground or a wall.
 - Projecting an image of the Sun can be as simple as punching a hole in a piece of paper.
 - You can also use a cereal box to make a more advanced version.
- **A pinhole projector works similarly to a camera, although instead of how a camera projects an image onto film (or a digital light detector), we are projecting the image of the Sun onto the ground.**
 - Simple cameras consist of a light-proof box (the camera body), a small hole that allows light to pass through (the aperture), and a lens inside the box to focus the light.
 - The hole in the paper functions similarly to the aperture of a camera, and the ground is the film/light detector.
 - The size of the aperture can be adjusted to increase or decrease the amount of light captured. A bigger opening allows more light in, making the image brighter, but less clear. A smaller opening allows less light in, making the image dimmer, but crisper.
 - A 5 mm hole is the optimal size for creating a crisp projection of the Sun from approximately 1 meter off the ground.
- **Do not attempt to take a picture of the Sun with a film or digital camera, without using a solar filter over the lens.**
 - If you want to try to take a picture of the solar eclipse with your camera using solar viewing glasses, place the glasses flush against the lens and you can view the Sun on your screen. You need to lower the exposure on your camera as low as it will go.

Explore the Map

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science.nasa.gov/learn/hepat

2024 Total Solar Eclipse U.S. Pinhole Projector Map

➤ How-to Video

Materials

- ❑ Precut 2D Map, printed on cardstock
 - ❑ Scissors
- ❑ Hole punchers
 - ❑ Circle
 - ❑ Star
 - ❑ One other shape

Other Pinhole Projector Options

Credit: NASA

<https://svs.gsfc.nasa.gov/14391/>

Try a colander!

Credit: NASA/Joy Ng

Stand under a tree!

Credit: NASA HEAT/Chantel Hunt Estevez

Simple Design with paper and aluminum foil.

Credit: NASA/JPL

<https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/edu/learn/project/how-to-make-a-pinhole-camera/>

Use your hands!

Credit: AAS

2024 Total Solar Eclipse U.S. Pinhole Projector Map

Discussion Questions

- What questions do you have about this activity?
- How would you modify this activity for your audiences?
- What other activities have you done that are similar to this one?

You are invited to add your ideas to the chat or raise your hand to share with the group.

How many people plan on doing this activity at their event?

Predict the Corona Activities

➤ Full Activity Instructions

- ★ Activity 1: Observing the Corona Through Time
- ★ Activity 2: Monitoring Sunspots Through the Solar Cycle
- ★ Activity 3: Predict the Corona for the April 8, 2024 with Chalk Art
- ★ Activity 4: Total Solar Eclipse Journal

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Activity 1: Observing the Corona Through Time
Early peoples recorded what they saw in the sky in words, drawings, riddles, and paintings. Examine these four images of the Sun's corona. What are these observations of the Sun? Record your observations.

1. Ancient rock art in Chaco Canyon may depict a total solar eclipse.
2. A drawing depicts the 1860 total solar eclipse. Additional eclipses, in various locations, also depicted what appear to be drawings. Credit: C. Tringali
3. This coronagraph image was taken by the SOHO space station, blocking the Sun to reveal its outer atmosphere.
4. This image of a total solar eclipse (2015) was taken with images on top of one another at different exposures. Credit: NASA

Observations of the Corona	Image 1	Image 2
Similarities		
Differences		

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Activity 2: Plotting Sunspots through the Solar Cycle
The Sun experiences seasons, similar to how Earth does. There are times when there is "stormy weather" and times of "good weather." Predict where in the solar cycle by graphing the number of sunspots.

Solar Cycle
Approximately every 11 years, the Sun's magnetic field reverses polarity. This is a change in the difference between an **active maximum** and an **active minimum**. The Sun at its active minimum has fewer sunspots and no coronal mass ejections. The Sun's magnetic poles also reverse.

1. Plot the sunspot number for each year which is when the maximum number of sunspots occur.
2. Plot the sunspot number for each year which is the minimum number of sunspots occur.
3. Predict the number of sunspots for the year 2024.

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Activity 3, Part 2: Predict the Corona for April 8, 2024 with Chalk Art
In Activity 1 you examined different images of the Sun's corona data to predict when solar maximum will occur. Based on the data in the corona and the solar cycle, make a prediction of what the April 8, 2024, total solar eclipse.

Materials:

- ☐ Cardstock Paper
- ☐ Black or Dark Blue Construction Paper
- ☐ White Chalk
- ☐ Scissors
- ☐ Tape (Optional)

Steps:

1. Trace a large circle (like a bowl or a cup) approximately 3 in. in diameter.
2. Carefully cut out the circle.
3. Place the circle template on construction paper and hold a circle or lines of chalk around the template a few times—10-15 times.
4. Holding the template in place with one hand, use the other from the circle, outward in all directions to represent the corona.
5. When you are done smudging, remove the circle. You're now like observers of the past did!

Activity 4 continued: Total Solar Eclipse Journal
Draw your observations:
Optional: make larger chalk art drawings like you did for your prediction.

Time: Phase (partial or total):		Time: Phase (partial or total):	
Time: Phase (partial or total):		Time: Phase (partial or total):	

How did your observations compare to your prediction?

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<https://science.nasa.gov/learn/heat/resource/predict-the-corona-activities-2/>

Predict the Corona Activities

➤ Abbreviated Tabletop Instructions & Talking Points for Outreach Events

Pro Tip!

Use half sheets of paper and a 3" diameter clear acrylic disk for the circular object.

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1QF4PV Bxze5L1MuH2w7rkP1CmBjIqKOBi/view?usp=share_link

The Solar Cycle
The corona looks differently during different phases of the solar cycle, displaying different features depending on the solar cycle phase.

Premainences
Bright strands of cooler, denser solar material suspended above the Sun's surface by magnetic fields.

Coronal Loops
Found near sunspots, these loops of solar material connect magnetic regions on the solar surface.

Total Solar Eclipses over Chile
March 20, 2015
Credit: S. Anabro, M. ...

Total Solar Eclipses over Argentina
July 23, 2019
Credit: Williams College Expedition Team

Solar Cycle Sunspot Numbers
The Solar Cycle is approximately 11 years, and higher activity, which is indicated by the number of sunspots.

Predict the Corona Chalk Talking Points

- The corona looks differently during each total solar eclipse, which depends on how active the Sun is.
 - The Sun experiences seasons, similar to how Earth does. There are times when there is "stormy weather" and times of "good weather." This is known as the solar cycle. (Refer to the Solar Cycle Tabletop.)
 - Scientists can track the solar cycle by counting the number of sunspots.
 - Scientists have been tracking sunspots since the 18th century and can accurately predict the solar cycle.
 - Solar Maximum is when the Sun is very active and has an increased number of sunspots.
 - Solar Minimum occurs when the Sun is less active and has a fewer number of sunspots.
- Sunspots are darker, cooler spots on the Sun where the Sun's magnetic fields are concentrated.
 - Magnetic energy increases in the Sun's atmosphere during solar maximum and the Sun's magnetic poles are flip-flopping.
 - Notice the features in the corona on image A. Prominences, coronal loops and helmet streamers are all caused by increased magnetic activity on the Sun. (Refer to the Solar Cycle Tabletop.)
 - Image A was taken during a total solar eclipse in 2015.
 - As you can see from the solar cycle sunspot progression graph, the Sun was very active during 2015.
 - Solar Maximum was in the year 2014, with a maximum average of 116 sunspots that year.
- Examine the corona in images B, C, and D. (Refer to the Imaging the Corona During Total Solar Eclipses Tabletop.)
 - What features do you see in these images? Prominences? Coronal loops? Helmet Streamers?
 - Where on the solar cycle did these total solar eclipses occur?
 - Consider these images in making your prediction for what the corona will look like on April 8, 2024.
 - Also consider the Solar Cycle Sunspot Progression graph. Do you expect a lot of magnetic activity on the Sun?

Predict the Corona Activities

➤ How-to Video

Materials

- ❑ Black or dark blue paper or cardstock
- ❑ Approx. 3" circular object for tracing
- ❑ White chalk

Predict the Corona Activities

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Extension Activity: Predict the Corona Cake Art

Try this delicious version of predicting the corona!

Total Solar Eclipse
Credit: NASA/Nat Gopalswamy

Credit: NASA HEAT/ Shannon Reed

Materials:

- ❑ 9" Circular Cake With Dark Icing or Frosting
- ❑ Powdered Sugar
- ❑ Approx. 3" Circular Object (an icing container lid works well)

Steps:

1. Bake a cake and frost it. Chocolate icing or frosting works well.
2. Place the circular object in the center of the iced cake. The circular object represents the Moon covering the Sun in the middle of the cake.
3. Sprinkle the powdered sugar around the circular object, creating shapes in the corona to match your prediction.
4. Remove the circular object. You've made total solar eclipse cake art! Take pictures of your corona cake and compare your prediction to your observations of the **April 8, 2024**, total solar eclipse.

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➤ **Bonus delicious extension activity!**
Make a Predict the Corona cake!

Materials

- ❑ 9" Circular Cake
- ❑ Dark Icing
- ❑ Powdered Sugar
- ❑ 3" round object

Predict the Corona Activities

Discussion Questions

- What questions do you have about this activity?
- How would you modify this activity for your audiences?
- What other activities have you done that are similar to this one?

You are invited to add your ideas to the chat or raise your hand to share with the group.

How many people plan on doing this activity at their event?

Ultraviolet (UV) Light-Reactive Bead Investigation

➤ Full Activity Instructions

- ★ Materials List
- ★ Learner Objectives
- ★ Detailed Steps
- ★ Background Information
- ★ Data Sheet
- ★ Bookmark

Experimenting with UV-sensitive Beads

By Deborah Scherzer, 2012

Introduction

Participants experiment with ultraviolet (UV) light-sensitive plastic beads, which are generally white but turn colors when exposed to UV light.

Materials Needed:

- 1 UV-sensitive bead per participant
- 1 pipette or straw per participant
- 1 bookmarker per participant
- Materials such as water, sunscreen, orange pill bottles, sunglasses, fabric, etc. for experimentation (see worksheet)
- 1 bookmarker (one per participant optional)
- Heavy paper or manila folders, glue, scissors (optional)
- Images of EM spectrum and SDO (optional)
- UV "check" light or flashlight if available (not available)

Target audience: Public science education events, informal science settings. Can be used to introduce the lecture on SDO's mission that utilizes UV light. More

Learner Objectives:

After the activity, students/participants should understand that:

1. The Sun produces light in all wavelengths, including invisible ultraviolet (UV)
2. UV can be dangerous and can burn our skin, damage our eyes, and destroy our cells.
3. The Earth's atmosphere provides significant, but not complete, protection from UV.
4. There are both ways to detect UV and also to protect ourselves from it.

Obtaining UV beads:

You can purchase UV beads from http://www.rockwell.com/uv

When gathering beads, 1 large coffee change from white to colored. Cool Note: Some other sunscreens do not sunscreens have corrected this defect.

Background:

These beads contain a special chemical that is an invisible type of light from the Sun's outer cells. Most UV is blocked through and can be detected. The big incident and fluorescent light is exposed to UV, usually from the Sun most UV rays they are emitting (4 white again). This process can be to the EM spectrum image)

Process:

1. Read the description above then if they understand that the example (e.g., each source of that cannot be detected by our eye)
2. Hand out beads and pipette/straw and make them. Have a bookmarker, if necessary. Then lay beads onto the pipette/straw of the bookmarker, and twist or tie it (it is no longer useful)
3. Now ask the students to be with their beads. Hand out but participants determine which way

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Final discussion:

Ask students which of the materials tested are light from the Sun? As a reflection class, let the UV radiation from the Sun? (and don't let them say at risk? [answer] Do not tell students)

Going Farther:

Show students the images following or current STEREO, or other missions taking imagery of colored. (They were taken in UV, which is not made from visible)

What wavelengths of light cause

Infrared	Visible
1000-700 nm	700-400 nm
Heat from the sun	Visible light we see
Heat from the sun	Visible light we see
Heat from the sun	Visible light we see

Beads are white >100 nm

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You be the scientist!

UV Bead Worksheet

Your prediction (What color will the bead be? Visible, UV, or color?)	Actual Color of Bead (color, UV, or color?)	Safe from UV?	Notes
Under water			
In sunlight			
In shadow			
Using sunscreen			
Cloudy sky			
Behind paper			
Behind sun glasses			
Under clear plastic			
Inside plastic orange soda/bottle			
Behind window glass			
Behind car windshield			
Under brim of cap			
Behind plastic			
Sun at mid-day			
Sun at sunset/sunrise			
UV (black) light			
Fluorescent light			
Incandescent light			
LED light			

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UV Bead Bookmarks

Stanford and Lockheed Martin Solar and Astrophysics Lab developed these bookmarks to support this lesson. The bookmarks briefly explain the electromagnetic spectrum and UV light.

To assemble bookmarks:

- Make copies of the patterns here.
- Have students cut them out and fold in half lengthwise.
- Cut a piece of cardstock the same size as the bookmarks.
- Fold the bookmark around the cardstock, and glue.
- Punch a hole in the top.

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<https://science.nasa.gov/resource/experimenting-with-uv-sensitive-beads/>

Ultraviolet (UV) Light-Reactive Bead Investigation

➤ Abbreviated Tabletop Instructions & Talking Points for Outreach Events

Pro Tip!

Have ~10 beads in several small 3oz cups to facilitate the activity.

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1yFb4rKtIX6CrOH9AsQHfv-8NRvIH2IL5?usp=share_link

UltraViolet (UV) Light-Reactive Beads

Light travels in waves and some waves have shorter wavelengths (UV-C). The beads will only react to the shorter wavelengths of UV.

Infrared	Visible	UV-A
1000-7000 nm	390-700 nm	400-315 nm

Makes our skin feel warm and can be detected by some animals such as snakes.

Can be seen by our eyes. It includes all the colors of the visible rainbow.

Too much exposure can result in the same damage as UV-B but to a lesser degree.

> 360 nm
Beads are White

Predict!
Before you expose the beads to sunlight, make a prediction about which materials block UV radiation.

Material
Cotton shirt
Polyester shirt
Hat brim
Sunglasses
Umbrella
Sunscreen
What other material do you think will block UV radiation?

Explore the Full Spectrum
science.nasa.gov/learn/heat

UltraViolet(UV) Light-Reactive Beads

Talking Points

- These beads react to Ultraviolet (UV) light.
 - UV light is just one type of light that the Sun emits.
 - The electromagnetic spectrum (EM Spectrum) is a distribution of frequencies of light that exist in the universe. (Refer to the EM Spectrum.)
 - The only portion of the EM spectrum that we can see is visible light.
 - All other light, including UV light is invisible to humans.
 - Some animals can see slightly into the UV portion of the spectrum (cats, pigs, cows, ferrets, and many other mammals can see).
 - Some animals can see slightly into the infrared portion of the spectrum (vampire bats, and some snake and beetle species).
- Some of the light on the EM spectrum is harmless to humans, and some frequencies of microwaves, infrared, UV light, and gamma rays, and other harmful wavelengths of light are harmful to your skin.
- The black light, or UV flashlight emits both UV light and some visible light.
- You cannot see the ultraviolet light coming from the flat EM Spectrum that purple visible light is very close to UV light which is why the flashlight emits both.
- NASA looks at the Sun in UV wavelengths to learn more about the solar atmosphere. (Refer to SDO Tabletop.)
- UV light can give us information about the temperature and density of the solar atmosphere, the corona.
- Why do you think these images of the Sun in Extreme UV colors? (If we didn't add color to the images, then we wouldn't be able to see them.)
- The AIA telescopes collect data, that is invisible to us. We can see it.
- Refer to <https://sdo.gsfc.nasa.gov/data/channels.php> for more information.

The Atmospheric Imaging Assembly (AIA) is a four-telescope array aboard SDO images the solar atmosphere in multiple wavelengths to link changes in the surface to interior changes.

NASA's Solar Dynamic Observatory (SDO) Studies the Sun in Multiple Ultraviolet Wavelengths

Why do images differ?
Hint: Ultraviolet light is invisible to humans.

AIA 1700 Å 4000 Kelvin Photosphere	AIA 4500 Å 6000 Kelvin Photosphere	AIA 171 Å 600,000 Kelvin Upper Transition / Quiet Corona
AIA 1600 Å 10,000 Kelvin Upper Photosphere / Transition Region / Chromosphere	AIA 304 Å 80,000 Kelvin Transition Region / Chromosphere	AIA 194 Å 800,000 Kelvin Upper Transition / Quiet Corona
AIA 211 Å 2 Million Kelvin Active Regions	AIA 335 Å 2.5 Million Kelvin Active Regions	AIA 094 Å 6 Million Kelvin Flaring Region

The Atmospheric Imaging Assembly (AIA) is a four-telescope array aboard SDO images the solar atmosphere in multiple wavelengths to link changes in the surface to interior changes.

THE ELECTROMAGNETIC SPECTRUM

Wavelength (meters): Radio, Microwave, Infrared, Visible, Ultraviolet, X-ray, Gamma Ray

Frequency (Hz): 10⁴, 10⁶, 10¹², 10¹⁵, 10¹⁶, 10¹⁸, 10²⁰

About the size of... Buildings, Humans, Honey Bee, Pinpoint, Protozoans, Molecules, Atoms, Atomic Nuclei

Ultraviolet (UV) Light-Reactive Bead Investigation

➤ How-to Video

Materials

- UV-reactive beads
- Fuzzy sticks or ribbon
- Data sheet
- Objects for experimenting with
 - Hat brim
 - Sunglasses
 - Cotton
 - Polyester
 - Umbrella
 - Sunscreen
- Optional bookmark
- Optional UV Flashlight

Ultraviolet (UV) Light-Reactive Bead Investigation

Discussion Questions

- What questions do you have about this activity?
- How would you modify this activity for your audiences?
- What other activities have you done that are similar to this one?

You are invited to add your ideas to the chat or raise your hand to share with the group.

How many people plan on doing this activity at their event?

How to Photograph a Solar Eclipse with your Smartphone

➤ Abbreviated Tabletop Instructions for Outreach Events

Q & A
with Dr.
Sten Odenwald

Annular Solar Eclipse over Albuquerque, NM 10/14/23.

Photo taken by an amateur with the iPhone 14 factory camera app using solar viewing glasses over the lens.

Credit: C.Milotte

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1hLxbPXjAqfQifw-x2Ga6pN5_IVeFCe/view?usp=share_link

National Aeronautics and Space Administration

How to Photograph the Solar Eclipse with your Smartphone

Steps:

1. Before pointing your camera at the Sun at any time other than during totality, remember to put a special-purpose solar filter over the camera lens. You can even use solar viewing glasses.
2. Adjust the Exposure.
During the partial phases of the solar eclipse, the Sun is intensely bright, so set the exposure as low as you can.
Example: iPhone 14 Factory Camera App

Access camera settings
Exposure setting
During the total phase of the solar eclipse, the light will significantly change and you will need to raise the exposure setting. *Remove the filter to photograph the total phase.*
3. Make sure your camera's flash is off, is adequately zoomed and in focus, and keep it steady, using a tripod if available.
4. Don't spend all of totality behind the lens of a camera! Look up and enjoy the moment! In some locations, totality can last up to 4 minutes.

 Learn more
<https://eclipse.aas.org/imaging-video/images-videos>

science.nasa.gov/learn/heat

A Guide to Smartphone Astrophotography by Dr. Odenwald

<https://spacemath.gsfc.nasa.gov/SMBooks/AstrophotographyV1.pdf>

Learn more about photographing solar eclipses

<https://eclipse.aas.org/imaging-video/images-videos>

How to Photograph a Solar Eclipse with your Smartphone

Photo montage of the August 21, 2017 total solar eclipse. **Taken with an iPhone 7-plus.**

Credit: Michael Murphy

August 21, 2017 total solar eclipse taken with an **iPhone 6** and a **30mm phone telephoto lens**. No filter was used so that the faint corona could be seen.

Credit: Fernando Labra

Digitally-enlarged shot with a **Samsung Galaxy S7 hand-held** and no telescope or telephoto with native camera at 1/50-seconds and ISO 50.

Credit: Joe Adlhoch

Yardstick Eclipse Demonstration

- Full Activity Instructions
- How-to Video with the Night Sky Network's Vivian White

Credit: Night Sky Network

Materials

- ❑ Meter Stick
- ❑ Binder Clips
- ❑ 1" (2.5cm) ball on a toothpick
- ❑ ¼" (7 mm) ball on a toothpick

<https://nightsky.jpl.nasa.gov/docs/ModelMeaningfulEclipses2016.pdf>

Contact: vwhite@astrosociety.org

My NASA Data Eclipse Activities for the Classroom

- Full Activity Instructions
- How-to Video with My NASA Data's Angela Rizzi

Credit: My NASA Data

<https://mynasadata.larc.nasa.gov/phenomenon/solar-eclipse>

Contact: angela.rizzi@nasa.gov

My NASA Data Phenomena

Phenomena listed under each sphere

Air Quality
Air Temperatures
Hurricane Dynamics
Urban Heat Island

Deforestation
Plant Growth Patterns
Phytoplankton Distribution

Land Use and Land Cover Change
Soil Moisture
Volcanic Eruptions

El Niño Southern Oscillation
Ocean Circulation Patterns
Sea Level Rise

Albedo Values
Sea and Land Ice Melt
Snow and Ice Extent

Earth's Energy Budget
Matter and Energy Cycles
Scale, Proportion and Quantity
Solar Eclipse
Systems and System Models

Solar Eclipse

Mini Lessons

How Does a Solar Eclipse Affect Air Temperature?

Students will examine air temperature data collected through The GLOBE Program during the 2017 US solar eclipse.

Solar Eclipse

Interactives

What is Space Weather?

In this interactive, students will learn the basics of space weather by engaging in a short interactive which introduces key terms: space weather, sunspot, solar flare, coronal mass ejection, and solar wind.

Solar Eclipse

Interactives

Solar Eclipse Story Map

In this story map, through a series of learning activities, students will examine the benefits and hazards of living with a star, describe and/or demonstrate how we use eclipses to study the Sun and its features, and investigate how our Sun may be used to learn about other stars and our universe.

Solar Eclipse

Lesson Plans

Modeling Solar Eclipse Geometry or Modeling Sun-Moon Positions for Solar Eclipses

In this lesson plan students will model the geometry of solar eclipses using quarters to represent the Sun and Moon (not to scale).

More Activities from NASA Partners

Solar Eclipse Journal

<https://observer.globe.gov/documents/19589576/51589943/EclipseJournal.pdf>

Our Place in the Universe, Sun, Earth, Moon, Eclipses Activity Guide

<https://www.nasa.gov/stem-content/our-place-in-the-universe-sun-earth-moon-eclipses-activity-guide/>

How Can the Little Moon Hide the Giant Sun?

<https://www.nasa.gov/stem-content/eclipse-how-can-the-little-moon-hide-the-giant-sun/>

How to Have a Successful Outreach Event

- **Limit the number of activities for your event**
 - We recommend 3-4, depending on the number of staff you have and your available space
- **Activities should just take a 3-5 minutes**
- **Set up your space so several people can do one activity at the same time**
 - *Recommend half of a 6' table per activity*
- **Have materials prepared before your event**
 - *Example: pre-cutting paper plates for Safe and Stylish Solar Viewing Glasses*
- **Have materials easily accessible for people as they approach your exhibit**
 - *Example: having ~10 UV-reactive beads in several small cups on the table*
- **Use Tabletop Instructions** to help visual learners with activities and to provide information to people who don't necessarily want to engage in a conversation
- **Ask people what they already know** about solar eclipses and let them share their experiences with you before launching into talking points

Activities Passport: Highly Recommended!

At our 10/14/23 Annular Solar Eclipse event in Albuquerque the activity passport was wildly successful!

SPECIAL EVENT!
Annular Solar Eclipse:
Saturday, October 14, 2023
solarsystem.nasa.gov/eclipses/2023/oct-14-annular/overview

Location	Partial Eclipse Begins	Annularity Begins	Maximum Annularity	Annularity Ends	Partial Eclipse Ends
Albuquerque, NM	9:13 AM	10:34 AM	10:35 AM	10:39 AM	12:09 PM

HANDS-ON ACTIVITIES
How to earn your NASA take-home packet:
Have your passport stamped after completing each activity. Once you complete four or more activities, visit the back of the NASA tent to receive a take-home packet.

- Annular Eclipse Selfie Station**
Take a selfie as you stand in front of the 2023 annular eclipse path map and scan the QR code to learn how to observe the 2023 annular eclipse safely.
- Ready, Set, Eclipse! DIY Eclipse Viewing**
Help you and your family safely view the eclipse with decorate-it-yourself eclipse glasses or pinhole projector to indirectly observe the Sun.
- Ready, Set Eclipse! Make a Prediction**
Predict the corona for April 8, 2024. NASA is preparing for the HelioPhysics Big Year. Learn about eclipses, the Sun, and more!
- Hubble Space Telescope 3D Experience**
The Hubble Space Telescope orbits the Earth 326 miles above the atmosphere to take pictures of outer space. Watch these photos come to life with our Augmented Reality experience, and use your hands to manipulate a 3D histogram of Hubble.
- Up, Up, and Away with Astrol!**
Take a quiz about NASA's astrophysics missions and learn how to see exoplanets transiting across their host stars!
- The Air We Breathe**
Learn about state-of-the-art methods that NASA is using to measure ozone and particulates in the air, including lidar and balloon soundings.
- GLOBE**
What happens to Earth when the Sun goes dark, even temporarily? Find out by measuring temperature and clouds with GLOBE! Play a cloud game and learn all the skills you need to be a volunteer eclipse scientist!
- WeatherSats Augmented Reality (AR)**
Earth-observing satellites like the Joint Polar Satellite System (JPSS) provide critical weather data. Use this AR app to learn about the satellites that monitor extreme weather and climate change.
- Flight Log**
Have you signed up for NASA's flight log? Fly your name on X-planes, print boarding passes, earn endorsement stamps, and build your own virtual flight log.

Place for participation stamp.

List of activities with a brief description.

Participants needed four stamps to earn a "NASA take-home packet," which included a NASA tote bag containing stickers, posters, and other NASA goodies.

2024 Activities Passport: Coming Soon!

A 2024 activity passport template is being developed so that the file can be edited to include the list of activities for individual events.

Add your location and eclipse times here.

Space for up to eight activities.

→ I will email you when it is published.

Total Solar Eclipse
April 8, 2024

Learn more!
<https://science.nasa.gov/eclipses/future-eclipses/eclipse-2024/>

Location	Partial Begins	Totality Begins	Maximum	Totality Ends	Partial Ends
edit	*time*	*time*	*time*	*time*	*time*

Hands-on Activities
Earn your NASA take-home packet by completing at least **four** activities. Then bring your passport to the **location** to receive your take-home packet.

- 1. Total Solar Eclipse Selfie Station**
Take a selfie in front of the 2024 total solar eclipse map and scan the QR code to learn how to safely observe the total solar eclipse.
- 2. Safe and Stylish Solar Viewing Glasses**
Decorate your solar viewing glasses, which you need to view the partial phases of the solar eclipse.
- 3. Predict the Corona Art**
During the total phase of the solar eclipse you will be able to see the Sun's outer atmosphere, the corona. What do you predict you will observe?
- 4. 2024 Total Solar Eclipse Map Pinhole Projector**
Solar viewing glasses are just one tool you can use to experience a solar eclipse. Try this pinhole projector to observe how the shape of the Sun changes through each phase of the eclipse.
- 5. *activity***
activity description

- 6. *activity***
activity description

- 7. *activity***
activity description

- 8. *activity***
activity description

Don't know how to answer a question?

Point visitors to a NASA Subject Matter Expert (SME).

At the Dallas Arboretum event we will identify our SMEs with name tags.

Want more background information on eclipse science and how NASA will study the 2024 total solar eclipse?

Try our three-part total solar eclipse training!

Part 1: Eclipse Essentials: Science, Safety, and NASA's Key Messages

Part 2: NASA Science and Eclipses: NASA Investigations, Missions, and More

Part 3: How to Participate in Eclipse Activities: About NASA Partners, Hands-on Activities, and Resources for Engaging Audiences of All Ages

- Each part takes approximately 30 minutes to complete.
- Choose to do one part or all three!
- Part 1 is required for NASA employees through the Satern learning platform.

<https://science.nasa.gov/learn/heat/resource/total-solar-eclipse-training/>

Have a great event!

Find all activity resources, including this presentation and the how-to videos here:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/18_93FsK0iwSu0CoiQCdO57zVEWy4MVV9?usp=share_link

Still have questions? Contact christina.h.milotte@nasa.gov

